

Romanian New Wave Cinema as Commemorative Critique of Communist Memory

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Abstract

The Romanian New Wave cinema (RNW) has been recognised as many things: a medium that addressed the inconsistencies in the way people felt about their historical trauma, a vernacular insertion nuancing declarations that Ceausescu was a “megalomaniacal dictator,” and a means to both attract and negotiate international interest in the country’s cultural output. But as well as these functions, RNW was a subversive critique of the “Western” memory of Romanian Communism. This article explores the self-conscious rejection implicit in RNW of the way that the Romanian past is packaged by Western, and Eastern, Europeans. Drawing on film theory, the tension between collective and individual memory, as well as the millennial impulse to debase “memory,” I argue that RNW was a self-conscious and creative effort at commemorating a past relevant for a democratic debate about the ways in which the past bears upon the present. As Russell Kilbourn suggests in relation to postmodern cinematography, RNW overcame the binary between individual and collective memory by showing cultural memories that were contemporarily relevant.

Keywords: Romanian New Wave – Memory – Transition – Europe – Cinema

Introduction

“I had a beautiful childhood during Ceaușescu’s regime.”¹⁷⁴ “Everyone had work ... the freezers were full.”¹⁷⁵ “People took care of each other.”¹⁷⁶ These vernacular memories from Romanian individuals are a curious confrontation for anyone anticipating a satellite microcosm of the “Evil Empire.”¹⁷⁷ But vernacular memories were inscribed into the films of Romanian New Wave cinema (RNW), a filmic movement that worked against and drew inspiration from an official memory-culture uneasy with satirical self-criticism. RNW – made in the first decade of the twenty-first century when Romania was seeking European and trans-Atlantic approval via the EU and NATO accession processes, as well as during domestic debate about the narrative of the communist past – was a critique and a qualification of what was Romanian memory.¹⁷⁸ These films were a self-conscious commentary on the relationship between then and now, and an expansion of what liminality meant for a country whose transition from communism to capitalism, from dictatorship to democracy, has been an extended experience.

RNW is an opportune lens for considering the availability of narrating history and the problem of authentic commemoration. The relationship between cinema and commemoration has received considerable attention amongst memory scholars since at least the 1970s, and visual images are understood as shaping and enabling a vision of collective memory.¹⁷⁹ Films thus perform a vital function in enabling collective access to a collective past. In Romania, this was important because a multifaceted debate on Communist memory remained lacking.¹⁸⁰ In the 1990s, the past was guarded by politics characterised by what memory-scholar Simona Mitroiu called “a lack of moral responsibility.”¹⁸¹ Only in 2012 did the Romanian parliament allow for the

¹⁷⁴ A Romanian with a portrait of Ceaușescu tattooed on his back, interviewed in Marina-Alina Asavei, “Nicolae Ceaușescu: between vernacular memory and nostalgia,” *Twentieth Century Communism* 11 (2016): 37.

¹⁷⁵ “Ceaușescu Auction Points to Lingering Nostalgia Among Romanians,” *France24*, January 31, 2018. <https://www.france24.com/en/20180131-ceausescu-auction-points-lingering-nostalgia-among-romanians>.

¹⁷⁶ “Many Eastern Europeans Feel Nostalgia for the Communist Era,” *The Economist*, October 12, 2017. <https://www.economist.com/europe/2017/10/12/many-eastern-europeans-feel-nostalgia-for-the-communist-era>.

¹⁷⁷ Harold Jackson, “From the Archive, 9 March 1983: Reagan calls Moscow an Evil Empire,” *The Guardian*, March 9, 2012. <https://www.theguardian.com/theguardian/2012/mar/09/archive-1983-reagan-russia-evil-empire>.

¹⁷⁸ The Romanian New Wave has been the subject of multi-disciplinary enquiry. Consensus is broadly that the movement is a barometer of social and cultural change. It has been explored as a site of remembrance, a record of the changing relationship of the artist in relation to politics, and a commentary on the relationship between history, identity and pride. Please refer to Onoriu Colacel, *The Romanian Cinema of Nationalism: Historical Films as Propaganda and Spectacle* (Jefferson: McFarland and Company, 2018); Michael Gott and Todd Herzog, *East, West and Centre: Reframing Post-1989 European Cinema* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2016); Anca Pusca, “Re-Thinking (Post) Communism after The Aesthetic Turn: Art and Politics in The Romanian Context,” *Journal of International Studies* 45 (2017): 233–240.

¹⁷⁹ Films provide us with the means to remember, making memories seem real, as Augustine understood: “Memory is not present to itself ... but only by means of an image of itself.” G. R. Edgerton and P. C. Rollins, eds., *Television Histories: Shaping Collective Memory in the Media Age* (Lexington: University Press of Kentucky, 2004), 8–12.

¹⁸⁰ Lavinia Stan, *Transitional Justice in Post-Communist Romania: The Politics of Memory* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013), 8–9, 18–21.

¹⁸¹ Simona Mitroiu, “Recuperative Memory in Romanian Post-Communist Society,” *Nationalities Papers* 44, no. 5 (2016): 754.

prosecution of individuals associated with communist crimes. RNW straddled the official condemnation of the crimes of communism in 2006, when President Basescu invoked twenty-one charges against the regime, but these performances of restorative justice were hardly likely to accommodate a democratic coming-to-terms with the past. This is because, in the demographic of those who wield power, ex-communists continued to dominate. RNW, made in this political climate, afforded a space for reflection, representing the past not as a fixed psychological or sociocultural concept, but as a dialogic compromise between memories.

If memory is an act of redemption of how we want the past to have been as much as how it feels in the present, as film scholar Thomas Elsaesser suggests, RNW rescued memories via an emotional aesthetic that constructed, as much as deconstructed, the “truth” of the past.¹⁸² Of course, as film scholar Russell Kilbourn recognised, “there is no way of gauging [the] objective accuracy or veracity vis-à-vis the “actual” past” in films.¹⁸³ Memory scholars broadly acknowledge “actual” past is attained in continuous dialogic compromise with the present, and the idea that Basescu could “settle” its memory is deconstructed by public intellectual Susan Sontag in her theory of collective memory as only a will “to value one thing over many others.”¹⁸⁴ Not only were these films confronting a past treated as “difficult,” but they were made in a socio-political context when access to the truth was politicised. Filmmakers of the late-twentieth and early twenty-first centuries were responding to a liberation in talking about Romania’s past, but uncertainty about the version of the past that would stand as the collective memory of “modern,” European Romania. They commemorated Communism as neither all good nor all bad, reflecting the postmodern moment they were made in, termed by Fredric Jameson as a “vacillation between performative celebration and lament for what has been lost.”¹⁸⁵ By putting Communism on screen, but Communism as worthy of celebration *and* lamentation, RNW was not an attempt to monopolise a collective memory. Rather, the films were sites of “resistance” against the very problem of collective consensus.¹⁸⁶ By reflecting on the narration of Romanian history, RNW thus reflected on the patterns of historical narration more broadly, calling for diversity and discursivity in what is remembered, and by whom.

This article will consider films that are concerned with the experience of “transition” (from communism to capitalism, or from anticipated revolutionary change to recognition of a failed one) symbolic of RNW, as well as the parallel positionality of Romania in and against Europe. Whilst

¹⁸² Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 60–62.

¹⁸³ Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 159.

¹⁸⁴ Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 228.

¹⁸⁵ Cited in Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 186.

¹⁸⁶ Gabriel Moshenska, “Working with Memory in the Archaeology of Modern Conflict,” *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* 1 (2010): 37–40.

RNW has received considerable scholarly attention, this paper seeks to locate the “European Question” at the heart of RNW, exploring films made during the negotiation of Romania’s entry into the European Union, that were simultaneously implicated in the debate about Europe’s future and its past. It begins by considering what Europe meant for RNW. These films were made in a moment of transnational concern about Europe and its peripheries. As historian Cristian Cercel implies, RNW challenged conceptualising Western Europe as the measure against which Eastern European identities are compared.¹⁸⁷ The second section focuses on the cinematic grammar of RNW, asking *how* films told the Romanian past. These films were provocative interventions, “cinematic international relations,” discussing the past in relation to the present.¹⁸⁸ These films did not prescribe a new canon but proposed a democratised expansion of commemoration. The final section considers the authorial ownership of commemorative history by examining the reception of RNW. It asks whose pasts these films should represent, and to whom. RNW legitimised individual experiences, calling for meaningful commemoration. As Kilbourn suggests in relation to postmodern cinematography, RNW overcame the binary between individual and collective memory by showing *cultural* memories that were contemporarily relevant.¹⁸⁹ To argue that RNW represented a subversive critique of the memory of Romanian Communism, this article challenges sociologist Manfred Steger’s theory of a Global Imaginary.¹⁹⁰ He suggests that as the forces of globalisation have disrupted local loyalties, there has been a growing consciousness of the world as a single whole. However, the philosopher Charles Taylor’s “social imaginary” insists that the memory of the collective is fundamental to its own conceptualisation. With this in mind, I will argue that the global imaginary is not global in its memory of history, but the product of Western norms and notions.¹⁹¹ This is clear in the way the international community imagines Romanian history and in its responses to RNW. Anca Pusca, the Romanian theorist, suggests that the “global imaginary” of Romanian history exaggerates 1989 as the “ultimate framing mechanism.”¹⁹² I am interested in how RNW challenged this imaginary, and argue that RNW sought to reframe 1989 as *the* reference point, calling for an expansion of what Romania had become in the early twenty-

¹⁸⁷ Cristian Cercel, *Romania and the Quest for European Identity: Philo-Germanism without Germans* (Milton Park: Routledge, 2020): 65.

¹⁸⁸ Anca Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution: The Romanian New Wave,” *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 24 (2011): 574.

¹⁸⁹ Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 204.

¹⁹⁰ Manfred B. Steger, *The Rise of the Global Imaginary: Political Ideologies from the French Revolution to the Global War on Terror* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008).

¹⁹¹ Guido M. Vaheeswiick, “The Philosophical Genealogy of Taylor’s Social Imaginaries,” *Journal of the History of Ideas* 78 (2017): 474–476.

¹⁹² Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 576.

first century. Whilst the global imaginary is *meant* to convey a single whole, RNW implied that the memory of the global imaginary excludes other memories of Communist Romania.

The Negotiation of Europe

There is something “irresistible” about Europe.¹⁹³ Whether promising “unending progress,”¹⁹⁴ or “soap, comfort and urbanity,”¹⁹⁵ the European essence has acquired an affective presence. Europe is not just an important idea to negotiate, but an *inescapable* idea to contend with.¹⁹⁶ Importantly, Europe is often imagined as *something* more than *somewhere*. Its territorial extent has been inconsistent, but somehow “ever and over-present,”¹⁹⁷ and for that reason, “Europe” is better understood as an idea, the supposed endpoint on the universal march to the equally evasive concept of Progress. Its pervasiveness is so powerful that it has become the global imaginary through which every other identity must negotiate.

But what *is* Europe? For the historian Ezequiel Adamovsky, it is a discursive formation for proving shared superiority.¹⁹⁸ For the cultural historian Ella Shohat, Europe represents “embedded narratives, buried premises, and submerged metaphors” that have cumulatively shaped a “common sense.”¹⁹⁹ RNW negotiated Europe-as-metaphor, as well as Europe as supplemented by a literary, legal, and political common culture. Europe, and its American big brother, had “colonised” the world’s institutions, including those that finance and broadcast films, such that its “sense of innate superiority” is assured by economic, political, and techno-cultural monopolies.²⁰⁰

The meaning of Europe, the ongoing debate about its conceptualisation and the contemporary concern about its territorial limits, served as the background against which RNW was being made.²⁰¹ Eastern European politicians used Europe as a symbolic aspiration, as rhetoric

¹⁹³ Roumen Daskalov and Diana Mishkova, *Entangled Histories of the Balkans – Volume Two – Transfers of Political Ideologies and Institutions* (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 2.

¹⁹⁴ Franz Liszt urged for Hungarian emulation, as quoted in Ivan Berend, *History Derailed: Central and Eastern Europe in the Long Nineteenth Century* (Berkeley: California University Press, 2003), 1.

¹⁹⁵ Eugen Filotti as quoted in Daskalov and Mishkova, *Entangled*, 45.

¹⁹⁶ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema: A Realism of Impressions,” *Film Criticism* 34 (2010): 27.

¹⁹⁷ Diana Mishkova, *We the People: Politics of National Peculiarity in Southeastern Europe* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2008), 5.

¹⁹⁸ Ezequiel Adamovsky, as quoted in Cercel, *Romania and the Quest*, 8.

¹⁹⁹ Ella Shohat and Robert Stam, eds., *Unthinking Eurocentrism: Multiculturalism and the Media* (Milton Park: Routledge, 2017), 364.

²⁰⁰ Shohat and Stam, *Unthinking Eurocentrism*, 1.

²⁰¹ Maria Todorova suggests that the Balkan identity was the “by-product” of constructing the European identity. She insists that the Balkan “space” was made in the minds of Western Europeans during the Enlightenment, and the force with which they insisted saw “Balkanism” established as a space and feeling synonymous with an *alter-ego* for the modern principles distinctive in the West. In this way, the “space” of Eastern Europe as a repository matters because it explains and exposes the prejudices applied to the region, as well as the semi-conscious re-enforcement of a strong “Western” identity. Maria Todorova, ed., *Balkan Identities: Nation and Memory* (London: Hurst and Company, 2004); D. Beyrau and M. Keck-Szajbel, “Eastern Europe as a ‘Sub-Germanic Space: Scholarship on Eastern Europe under National Socialism,” *Kritika: Explorations in Russian and Eurasian History* 13 (2012): 691.

to inflict national shame, absorbing its essentialism as well as the unequal relationship unavoidable when engaging with its institutional form.²⁰² The role of the filmmaker was subtle, distance from formal diplomatic negotiations gave space for satirising both the European idea, as well as its negotiation by state representatives. According to Roumen Daskalov there has been a continuum of engagement in cultural spaces, between wholesale emulation and total cultural autarchy.²⁰³ RNW represented one artistic space querying the Romanian relationship with the West but followed similar cultural endeavours. The *Junimist* columnist Constantin Radulescu-Motru called political aping of European practices “forms without substance” in the interwar period, and suggested Romania should forge its own culture.²⁰⁴ At the same time, Radulescu-Motru’s lament that Europe was embraced ineffectively has artistic and political precedents. In the 1920s, the Romanian literary scholar Eugen Lovinescu advocated cultural synchronism, believing that modernity would come through “adapting and processing” Western models.²⁰⁵ These anxieties were rhetorically dialled up in the twenty-first century by those concerned with the corruption of Romanian sensibility and used as more justification for European tutelage.²⁰⁶ This included the narration of European memory.²⁰⁷ Numerous scholars have recognised that the “self-evidential triumph” of the “West” has a “taken-for-granted quality,” 1989 elaborated according to the “coloniser’s model of the world.”²⁰⁸ “Qualification” for the EU, synonymous in parlance and politics as “proper Europe,” is based on measurable Europeanness (read Western-ness). It is presumed ECE fails *unless* and *until* it demonstrates sufficient “Europeanness.” Leaving aside the argument of Polish-American historian Piotr Wandycz that the “exceptional European” traits of the West owe considerable historic debt to the “East,”²⁰⁹ geographer Merje Kuus considers the enlargement of the EU and NATO as judged according to a “gradation of Europeanness or Eastness.”²¹⁰ The physical location of ECE states matters little, but the concept of Eastness means they are competing in the same “perceptual space” that has plagued them time immemorial.²¹¹ Success is conditional. In part, it

²⁰² Jussi Sakari Jauhianen, “New Spatial Patterns and Territorial-Administrative Structures in the European Union: Reflections on Eastern Europe,” *European Planning Studies* 22 (2014): 697–698.

²⁰³ Daskalov and Mishkova, *Entangled Histories*, 96.

²⁰⁴ Diana Stanciu, “Forms without Substance or Synchronism? Attempts to Define Culture and Civilisation in Early Twentieth-Century Romania,” *European Review of History* 20 (2013): 45–47.

²⁰⁵ Stanciu, “Forms without Substance,” 56.

²⁰⁶ Interview in Robert D. Kaplan, “The Fulcrum of Europe: Romania longs for the West, and the West needs Romania more than it knows,” *Atlantic Monthly* (1998): 28–36.

²⁰⁷ Explored in David Lowenthal, *The Past is a Foreign Country* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015).

²⁰⁸ Mats Braun, “EU Climate Norms in East-Central Europe,” *Journal of Common Market Studies* 52 (2014): 447; J. M. Blatt in Shohat and Stam, *Unthinking Eurocentrism*, 2.

²⁰⁹ The connection between Lord Byron and Greek nationalism, and British Gladstonian politics and the impetus of Bulgarian nationalism, are explored in P. S. Wandycz, “The Price of Freedom,” 5.

²¹⁰ M. Kuus, “Europe’s Eastern Expansion and the Reinscription of Otherness in East-Central Europe,” *Progress in Human Geography* 28 (2004): 476.

²¹¹ A. Schwell, “Negotiating the Imagined Geography of Europeanness in Polish State Bureaucracies,” *Anthropological Journal of European Cultures* 24, no. 2 (2015): 128.

is accepting the Western model of democratisation and market capitalism.²¹² It is also, for political scientist Maria Mälksoo, about subscribing to “the European account” of history that removes any moral guilt in the West. The Estonian President Lennart Meri summarised this well in the 1990s by remarking that although everyone was talking about the death of communism no one had seen its body.²¹³ Ultimately, it seems, to be “European” is to *no longer be Eastern*. The concept of “overstretch,” attributed to the British historian Paul Kennedy, was in the rhetoric of the Chairman of the EU Convention in 2002: including Turkey would destroy the very “idea” of Europe.²¹⁴ Europe was a space and identity whose limits would stretch to include (and exclude) an ECE of artificial acceptability.

RNW, at the turn of the century, could be understood as literary scholar Michael Rothberg’s “art of transition,” an aesthetic for working through transitional periods. Western Europe, the EU, and NATO were blended in these films just as they were being blended in the geopolitical discourse regarding Romanian positionality vis-à-vis the “West.” As Cercel argues, RNW challenged conceptualising Western Europe as the measure against which identities are compared, thereby “not showing how European Romania is but rather showing how Romanian Europe is.”²¹⁵ Given that RNW films were being made as accession negotiations were at their peak, they were live commentary on the Romanian relationship with Europe, including its genealogy.

The Western imaginary of Communism is challenged in Cătălin Mitulescu’s 2006 film, *The Way I Spent the End of the World*. Told from the perspectives of two children, Eva and Lalailu, the film follows their schooltime experience before 1989. After Eva and her boyfriend accidentally break a bust of Ceaușescu, they are sent to a reformatory school where Eva meets Andrei, the son of dissidents, and the two begin training for their escape Westward. Lalailu prepares revenge on Eva’s behalf by conspiring to kill Ceaușescu. The warm palette of outside spaces, however, juxtaposes these plans against sunny summers. This is a pre-revolutionary past, full of love, rather than the evil applied broad-brush to pre-1989 Romania. Nonetheless, the suffering endured under Communism is recognised: food insecurity is remembered when a slice of cheese is split three ways.²¹⁶ Film historian Mihaela Petrescu thinks, therefore, that this film reveals the implausibility

²¹² A. Stenning, “Out There and in Here: Studying Eastern Europe in the West,” *Area*, 37 (2005): 380.

²¹³ Maria Mälksoo, “The Memory Politics of Becoming European: The East European Subalterns and the Collective Memory of Europe,” *European Journal of International Relations* 15 (2009): 661–663.

²¹⁴ Sami Moisis, “Redrawing the Map of Europe: Spatial Formation of the EU’s Eastern Dimension,” *Geography Compass* 1 (2007), 98.

²¹⁵ Cercel, *Romania and the Quest*, 65.

²¹⁶ *The Way I Spent the Rest of the World*, directed by Cătălin Mitulescu, produced by In-Ah Lee, Philippe Martin, Catalin Mitulescu, Daniel Mitulescu and David Thion (*Les Films Pelléas*, 2006), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/the-way-i-spent-the-end-of-the-world>.

of nostalgic commemorations of Communist Romania. Indeed, nostalgia *had* to be pictured in summer: in winter, the average temperature inside a Bucharest apartment was eight degrees.²¹⁷

But the film challenges the self-appointed importance of the West. Eva changes her mind in attempting to cross the Danube, despite overcoming the intense cold-water training against hypothermia, which is perhaps symbolic of the conditionality for European access. Eva makes it eventually, pictured on a cruise ship heading west. Her expressions are remorseful rather than happy, in contrast to earlier scenes. As the director explained, “I wanted very much to see a film about the Ceaușescu era...we lived in those times and have those memories. At one point the revolution came over us...and we got lost.”²¹⁸ Andrei might have made it to Italy, but this no longer gives Eva a sense of purpose. We watch her contemplate the sacrifices required of leaving and the sacrifices of domestically “transitioning,” receiving news that Alex died in the revolution. This film suggests that the *dream* of the West is better than the West turns out to be.

Leaving to make it, or staying to save it, was an important concern in contemporary Romania, heightened in accession discourse emphasising an East-West slope and making real the chance to experience the long-imagined West.²¹⁹ Between 2000 and 2015, 15% of the population left to go abroad, suggesting that the West remained “the land of abundance in the Romanian imagological consciousness.”²²⁰ Therefore, *The Way* looked to the past to communicate with the present. Eva sends back remittances, which hints at post-communist inflation and unemployment. Her coming-of-age coincided with Romania’s transition, but Eva does not transition to a promised land. She, like Romania in 2006, is lost, approaching the West according to the deadline of the Thessaloniki Summit, but not necessarily the better for it.

Eva’s tension between wanting to reap the benefits of the European “lifeworld,” and resistance to absorbing its account of the past is also clear in accession negotiations.²²¹ Amongst politicians, there was an explicit embrace of all things Western, premised on legitimating Romania’s synonymity via rhetoric pretending a temporal lag in development. In the words of one official, Romania needed tutelage to turn a “nation of weak, fuzzy institutions” into members of the “family” of civilised countries.²²² This included playing into a “domestic orientalism” surmountable

²¹⁷ “Remembering life in Romania under communist rule,” *The Economist*, September 1, 2015, <https://www.economist.com/prospero/2015/09/01/remembering-life-in-romania-under-communist-rule>.

²¹⁸ Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 581.

²¹⁹ Cercel, *Romania and the Quest*, 11–14.

²²⁰ UN Report in Adriana Cordali Gradea, “The Rhetoric of leaving, or the mirage of the fetishized West in Cristian Mungiu’s *Occident*,” *Journal of European Studies* 48 (2018): 251.

²²¹ Alexandra Gheciu, “Security Institutions as Agents of Socialisation? NATO and the ‘New Europe,’” *International Organisation* 4 (2005): 979; Constantinescu, as quoted in Kaplan, “The Fulcrum of Europe,” 34.

²²² Civil servant Dorel Sandor, as quoted in Kaplan, “The Fulcrum of Europe,” 32.

by self-stereotyping “ostensibly at their own collective expense.”²²³ Getting into Europe required internalising its spatial moral language. However, Eva, and RNW, showed that hearts and minds did not automatically change in the process.

Image 1: Luci and Sorina discuss the advantages of staying or leaving in Cristian Mungiu’s 2002 film, *Occident*.

Cristian Mungiu’s *Occident* more explicitly challenged the problem of existential choice that envisions the West as the dreamland in a precarious post-communist landscape.²²⁴ The tragicomedy is concerned with the experience of young people moving to the West to overcome the difficulty of employment and financial success in Romania. *Occident* was made in 2002, before Romania’s successful bid for EU membership. Three episodes explore the binary position that if the “East” was home, then the “West” was the fix. In the first episode, Luci and Sorina wrestle with unemployment, and Sorina starts looking for a rich Westerner, an undefined symbolic gateway, “anywhere but this shitty place.” Luci continues his struggle in Romania, therefore only able to “*imagine* how it would be like to eat at McDonald’s every Saturday!”²²⁵ Figure One evidences

²²³ M. Buchowski’s concept, then M. Herzfeld, both as quoted in in Schwell, “Negotiating the Imagined Geography,” 143.

²²⁴ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema,” 26.

²²⁵ *Occident*, directed by Cristian Mungiu, produced by Dan Badea and Dan Bade (Temple Film, 2002), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/occident>.

the unlikely chance of finding a hamburger.²²⁶ Certainly, Communism is not remembered as the solution to present-day malaise: shots of socialist-era apartment blocks symbolise the struggle Romania has passed through. *Occident* queries the fetishization of the West as redemptive. Focusing on personal encounters with the East/West question, Mungiu reminds the audience that “the microcosm of the everyday individual is always in relationship with the larger social body” and the complexity of life is navigated at the individual as much as the ideological level.²²⁷ These characters are disappointed by New Europe and contemplate leaving because “their [own] lives seem futureless.”²²⁸ Luci’s brother Nica does leave, but remains absent, symbolic of the immaterial imaginary of the West. News of his death shatters the idea of the West as paradise, but the East is not much better. Luci only finds employment in a full-body beer bottle suit via nepotistic bribery. As he hums the Communist propagandistic song, “*Did you ever expect the year 2000 to look this way?*,” the hollowness of the West as redemptive is laid bare.

In the second episode, the West is represented as the land of opportunity via the Marriage Bride Agency, a match-making service for Eastern brides and Western grooms. For Mihaela, it is also the place where she might receive recognition for her poetry. A belief in the liberating modernity of Western culture encouraged an exodus in the late nineteenth century when creatives sought cultural education in Paris. She dreams of escape via the “French gateway,” like her parents in their attempt to find her a partner.²²⁹ Again, Romania’s present-day failings are interrogated as much as the perception of a Western solution. Playing into contemporary agonies, corruption is made evident in gifts to the agency, and the state is presented as pitifully weak via the dishevelled appearance of the police. This film captures the retrogression of the new world, which, still in 2020, frustrated one politician as “demotivated.” The police in *Occident*, like the Romanian bureaucracy, “don’t give a fuck about anything.”²³⁰

The historian Diana Georgescu offers an interesting reading of the symbolic coding in the gendered experiences in *Occident*, vis-à-vis Europe. She finds encrypted critique on the negotiation of the European “marriage” of background geopolitics. The Romanian male characters are presented as failing to live up to the role of romantic heroes, or to financially provide for their

²²⁶ Image taken from “Cristian Mungiu’s *Occident* (2002),” *East European Film Bulletin*, December 9, 2017, <https://eefb.org/retrospectives/cristian-mungius-occident-2002/>.

²²⁷ Angelina Ilieva and Esther Peters, “Interview with Lenuta Siukin on The Romanian New Wave,” *East from Chicago*, March 30, 2018, <https://lucian.uchicago.edu/blogs/eastfromchicago/2018/03/30/interview-with-lenuta-giukin-on-the-romanian-new-wave/>.

²²⁸ Julie Paulesc, “Between Eastern Roots and Western Wings: (Re)Mapping the Pursuit of Happiness in Cristian Mungiu’s Movie *Occident*,” *Economics, Management, and Financial Markets* 6 (2011): 236.

²²⁹ Adela Beiu, “The Nation and the Absurd: A Romanian Story of Modernity,” *Modernism/modernity* 21 (2014): 961–978.

²³⁰ “Why Balkan doctors head for western Europe,” *The Economist*, December 16, 2020, <https://www.economist.com/europe/2020/12/16/why-balkan-doctors-head-for-western-europe>

families. They symbolise a weak nation in contrast to the Western men, who arrive in shiny cars and as prospective, professional spouses.²³¹

Mihaela and her family anticipate marriage with the West, but they are shocked when the West arrives as a Mozambique-born Italian citizen. However, his ability to understand the family (thanks to the Latinity of the Roman language) reverses the framework dividing West and East into territorial and ideational certainties. His meeting with the dolled-up Romanian representative takes place over dinner in the family's house, redecorated to stress the origin of the Romanian nation within Europe with two portraits, one of the Dacian king, Decebalus, and the other of the Roman emperor, Trajan. For Georgescu, these portraits, in the context of EU accession, "are meant to strike a balance between the indigenous and the broader European components in national identifications."²³² The performance of the family is similarly framed in mainstream geopolitics about Romania "winning" its seat in the Western socio-cultural imaginary, welcoming "foreigners with an absurd mixture of imbecility and kindness."²³³ Marriage into male Europe is in dialogue with contemporary discourses, that Romania somehow fails its obligation to provide for its people the life they want without Western wedlock. *Occident* challenges these frames by offering neither happy marriages nor easy answers, engaging with Romanian-ness in relation to her European fiancée.

In *Occident* the West is not imagined as redemptive to domestic ills and nor is the Western imaginary. As the cultural theorist Adriana Cordali Gradea argues, the compilation into three unresolved stories that all revise 1989 as the harbinger of progress mirrors the splintering of rhetorical master-narratives behind labels like "pre" and "post" Communism. Communism, transition and democracy, concepts applied by EU diplomats to explain Romania's present and summarise Romania's past, are challenged in cinema undermining the ideological framing of binaries behind East and West.²³⁴

Ultimately, RNW mirrored its context in challenging the idea of Europe. At the political level, calls to remake the European memory were necessarily judicious. Eastern Europe had no shared past that could match the strength-in-consensus of the long maturation of the Western counterfactual.²³⁵ 1989 meant something local, the following decade something national, and the experience of socialism was remembered, according to the historian Claudia-Florentina Dobre

²³¹ Diana Georgescu, "Marrying into the European Family of Nations: National Disorder and Upset Gender Roles in Post-Communist Romanian Film", *Journal of Women's History* 23 (2011): 137-145.

²³² Georgescu, "Marrying into the European Family," 142.

²³³ Ieta, "The New Romanian Cinema," 28.

²³⁴ Adriana Cordali Gradea, "The Rhetoric of Leaving," 250.

²³⁵ Malgorzata Pakier and Joanna Wawrzyniak, eds., *Memory and Change in Europe: Eastern Perspectives* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2015).

explores, as “a scale from black to pink to grey.”²³⁶ To challenge the European discourse of the twentieth century was “awkward,” because it meant “reminding the West of their co-responsibility for the complexity of the region’s immediate past.”²³⁷ Strategic subversion was clear in the content of RNW. These films explored Western discourses on Communist memory and its prejudices in relation to life pre-1989. Ironic self-abasing was a foil for these bigger questions. As the historian Lucian Boia points out: “there is a long way to go before “Romanians will be able to regard Westerners with the same detachment (or indifference) with which the Westerners regard them.”²³⁸ Attempts to be counted as European, or to make Europe count, exposed the centrality of the European idea. However, the aesthetics of the films, the subject of the next section, exposed the fragility of the European idea, suggesting a self-awareness that the West meant more than its own self-definition.

Ambivalent Aesthetics

If Hollywood histories “puree” the past into “digestible bits of information,”²³⁹ RNW films are quasi-inedible. Its grammar, for film scholar Karl Schoonover, “turns boredom into a kind of special work,” in which “seeing becomes a form of labour.”²⁴⁰ Fast-paced narratives and easy answers were rejected. Filmmakers preferred the affective intimacy of slow cinema and associative minimalism, demanding an attentive spectator.²⁴¹ Communist memory was approached with post-modern non-judgement, the personal past the privileged subject. RNW reconstructed, empathetically, stories “to convey how historical people witnessed, understood, and lived their lives.”²⁴² Several filmmakers associated with RNW explained their practices as attempts to honour individual memories. Radu Muntean called for a restoration of authenticity, his film *The Paper Will be Blue* (2006) which was about the night of the revolution in Romania, was “made not to discover the truth about the revolution” but “to tell the story of [its] people.”²⁴³ Mitulescu wanted to “tell” the Ceaușescu era, but also “the [stories] of my childhood” and “the happiness and sadness that

²³⁶ Claudia-Florentina Dobre, “Uses and Misuses of Memory: Dealing with the Communist Past in Postcommunist Bulgaria and Romania,” in *Memory and Change*, edited by Pakier and Wawrzyniak, 300–310.

²³⁷ Mälksoo, “The Memory Politics of Becoming European,” 653–680.

²³⁸ Lucian Boia in Gott and Herzog, eds., *East, West and Centre*, 156.

²³⁹ Frank Sanello in Marnie Hugh-Warrington, *The History on Film Reader* (Milton Park: Routledge, 2009), 1.

²⁴⁰ In Anne Fuchs, *Precairous Times: Temporality and History in Modern German Culture* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press), 119–120.

²⁴¹ Raluca Jacon, “Romania: Transnational and National Tensions Beyond the New Wave,” in Lydia Papdimitriou and Ana Grgic, *Contemporary Balkan Cinema: Transnational Exchanges and Global Circuits* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2020), 173.

²⁴² R. J. Raack, “Historiography as Cinematography: A Prolegomenon to Film Work for Historians,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 18 (1983): 418.

²⁴³ Staff writer, “Reconstruirea Atmosferei Capitalei Din Decembrie 1989,” *Cinemagia* (2006).

came with them.”²⁴⁴ Corneliu Porumboiu was not seeking absolute truth in his film about the memory of the revolution, *12:08, East of Bucharest* (2006), but was interested in why 1989 still “percolates in people’s minds.”²⁴⁵ These films were not prescriptive histories, but mediums for *discursive* representation.

RNW filmmakers used the past to communicate with the present, which was an established idea in memory scholarship of Romanian history, especially at the turn of the century.²⁴⁶ The post-1989 project, which the German writer Peter Schneider believed was only ever about “dreams of European hegemony,” had failed.²⁴⁷ But rather than blame the past, RNW visualised a period let down by the so-called promised land. RNW mirrored nineteenth-century nostalgia, a longing for an irrecoverable moment, but was postmodern in its self-awareness about the absurdity of searching for the lost time of the Pitesti experiment.²⁴⁸ Hence, nostalgia was “ironised,” in the words of Linda Hutcheon, which remembers the past not to restore Friedrich Nietzsche’s monumental past, a “greatness that once existed,” but to critique its context.²⁴⁹ RNW addressed history but did so to disrupt the idea that history is prescribed in pursuit of a non-specific trans-Atlantic teleology.

Image 2: The family discuss how best to kill the pig without attracting unwelcome attention, in *The Legend of the Greedy Policeman*, the fourth episode in Mungiu’s 2009 collection, *Tales from the Golden Age*.

²⁴⁴ Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 580.

²⁴⁵ Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 579.

²⁴⁶ Andreas Huyssen, “Present Pasts: Media, Politics, Amnesia,” *Public Culture* 12 (2000): 21–38.

²⁴⁷ Peter Schneider, “The Other Europe,” *Salmagundi*, no. 166/167 (2010): 22–37.

²⁴⁸ The Pitesti Prison was the location of the notorious “re-education campaign” in which prisoners were subject to methods of torture.

²⁴⁹ Friedrich Nietzsche, *Untimely Meditations*, 2nd Edition (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997): 69.

The collection of six shorts set in late communism, *Tales from the Golden Age* (2009), invites an expanded memory of the Communist period. Each one revolves around contemporary “legends” of the time, its title referencing the propagandised “Golden Age” and its content exposing the challenges of reality. The memory-scholar Eyal Zandberg suggests that commemorative discourse plays a distinctive role in performing cultural trauma and a vital one recuperating from it. Comedy insists on a rebellion against the given.²⁵⁰ *Tales* rebels with humour, conveying the depth of past tragedy and failure of the present by eliciting laughter as catharsis. Deliberately ironic and replete with invitations for inference, Communism is performed as a “Kafkaesque territory of inane party activists, inept yet feared policemen, intrepid small-time dealers, and harassed citizens.”²⁵¹ No episode condemns the past, but they commemorate it in carnivalesque good cheer. Implicit is the insistence that the Communist memory should accommodate the perspectives of harassed citizens too.²⁵²

In *The Legend of the Greedy Policeman*, familial cooperation juxtaposes with the candours of Communism, when a brother delivers a pig to his brother’s apartment. His family are only partly pleased: figure 2 shows the tension between gifts and gratitude in a society rife with jealousy over food availability, because of rationing enforced in the 1980s.²⁵³ The industrialisation of the 1970s following Ceaușescu’s pursuit of unabridged socialist modernity triggered mass urban migration. However, these populations remained dependent on the countryside to be fed, especially because Ceaușescu responded to increasing international debts by exporting all agricultural produce.²⁵⁴ The resulting intimacy of a semi-urban, semi-rural state is given tragicomic treatment via images of decaying apartment blocks, and the contrasting costumes of the policeman and his brother. However, comedy pervades the legend: to enjoy the gift of a pig involves gassing it to death. The absurdity of the system, when neither urban nor rural realities functioned properly, is embodied when the family blows up their apartment, having failed to empty the canister. This is a whimsical treatment of the Communist version of a Golden Age. It might have been full of greyness and gas, but it was also replete with gaiety.

²⁵⁰ Eyal Zandberg, “Ketchup in the Auschwitz of Tomatoes’: Humour and the Collective Memory of Traumatic Events,” *Communication, Culture and Critique* 8 (2015): 108–111.

²⁵¹ Monica Filimon, “Reviewed Work(s): *Tales from the Golden Age* by Cristian Mungiu, Oleg Mutu, Ioana Uricaru, Hanno Höfer, Razvan Marculescu and Constantin Popescu,” *Cineaste* 37 (2012): 54.

²⁵² *Tales from the Golden Age*, Dir. Hanno Höfer, Cristian Mungiu, Constantin Popescu, Ioana Uricaru and Răzvan Mărculescu, Produced by Cristian Mungiu, Pascal Caucheteux and Oleg Mutu (Mobra Films, 2009), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/tales-from-the-golden-age>.

²⁵³ Image taken from “Where There’s Pomp ... Cristian Mungiu on *Tales from the Golden Age*,” *British Film Institute*, April 29, 2014. <https://www2.bfi.org.uk/news/where-there-s-pomp-cristian-mungiu-tales-golden-age>.

²⁵⁴ “Remembering Life in Romania Under Communist Rule,” *The Economist*, September 1, 2015, <https://www.economist.com/prospero/2015/09/01/remembering-life-in-romania-under-communist-rule>

In *The Legend of the Party Photographer*, a desperate attempt to satisfy a state that cared more about presentation than performance is captured in hurried revisions of a newspaper to ensure a photograph of Ceaușescu next to the French president sees him with an equally authoritative hat. However, Ceaușescu ends up wearing *and* holding a hat, hinting at a disorganised state in disarray. Most screen time is given to long shots of the corridor, following middlemen as they trip shuffle between implicated offices. Unlike Western aesthetics that, according to film-scholar Mary Doane, deals with “duration” by condensing it to become “eminently meaningful,” these characters squander time in luckless confusion.²⁵⁵ A committed spectator is demanded by such authentic treatment of time, unfamiliar for those used to its capitalist commodification in entertainment.²⁵⁶ This episode offers nostalgic, well-intentioned cooperation, achieved in the multi-layering of scenes and the noisiness of the revision process. Taking overt manipulation of the “truth” as its subject, it implicitly queries the futility of searching for a single truth at all.

By combining multiple vignettes, folkloric in their celebration of Romanian camaraderie, *Tales* inscribed oral history onscreen. Non-linear scenes reject the hero-dominated narratives of Hollywood fare. Villagers, policemen, and interns all have stories worth remembering in realism-without-borders, the idea that everything is worthy of being the subject of a film. *Tales* is not confrontational, but it questions the pursuit of any single past, suggesting that polyphonic pasts deserve legitimation.

What deserves commemoration is similarly revised in *12:08, East of Bucharest*. Specifically, the movie questions whether the Romanian Revolution *was* a revolution, and whether Romania overcame Communism. In asking questions that periodically resurface in contemporary forums, the film scholar Dominique Nasta considers the film a comprehensive study of the post-communist psyche.²⁵⁷ Set in a Moldavian town, the film explores the feeling of change for people outside Bucharest via a TV call-in show, a pensioner, a journalist and a teacher standing in for all those left out of the “Issue of the Day.”²⁵⁸ *12:08* is about being lost in transition. That little has changed is inscribed in the film’s opening and closing in the same faded, desaturated cityscape. The poverty-stricken town on both sides of the accounts of the past queries the significance of 1989 as pre-revolutionary and post-revolutionary realities appear blurred. The amateur camerawork in the studio means that the questions surrounding the revolution appear “almost as

²⁵⁵ Mary A. Doane, *The Emergence of Cinematic Time: Modernity, Contingency, the Archive* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2002): 163.

²⁵⁶ Tinda Kendall’s concept as quoted in Fuchs, *Prekarious Times*, 119.

²⁵⁷ Alan Riding, “Cameras were Ready: The Revolution Wasn’t,” *New York Times*, June 3, 2007, <https://www.nytimes.com/2007/06/03/movies/03ridi.html>.

²⁵⁸ *12:08, East of Bucharest*, directed by Corneliu Porumboiu, produced by Daniel Burlac (42 Km Film, 2006), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/1208-east-of-bucharest>.

a joke, an opportunity to distract oneself from the otherwise obvious lack of change.”²⁵⁹ Like the cameraman, who lets his camera fall, the viewer is not offered an absolute answer. They infer, though, that whether one was a “doer” or a “non-doer” in this supposedly seminal moment, no single memory permits knowing whether Romania has arrived in its post-Communist Promised Land.

The staging of the conversation in a TV studio is important because it was on television that most people witnessed the revolution. However, *12:08* reviews the role of the camera, suggesting it be less an “investigative” tool than a “recovery” tool, enabling recovery from framing the revolution as defining Romanian history.²⁶⁰ The media is presented as a space for democratic discussion, call-ins indulging nostalgia as well as ex-Radio Free Europe listeners. No real answers emerge, and the audience hears how the guest Piscoci spent *his* 12:08: giving magnolias to his wife, “the very same day some people appeared on TV to tell us revolution had won.” It is hard not to read from the host’s sarcastic comment of the camerawork, “At last, a close-up!,” that *12:08* offers a close-up of the diversity of Romanian individuals in 1989, who were so much more than what one reviewer imagined as “passively swept up in historical events, like crumbs pushed along by a ragged broom.”²⁶¹

This film suggests that different questions need to be asked about post-communist lives. Indeed, the characters become more concerned with justifying their post-communist existence. 1989 might have been symbolic, briefly, but for many Romanians, it was a long way from their preoccupations. The talk-show host’s stutter, especially over “exceptionality,” invokes the revolution’s framing, as does the teacher’s instruction, “I don’t want to ruin your Christmas time. Write about what you know—the French Revolution is okay, if nothing else works for you.” The past does not need to ruin the present, once shackled of its exceptionality.

The symbolism of 1989 is similarly revisited in *The Death of Mr. Lazarescu* (2005). Set in 2000, but with evidence of a staid, neo-communist healthcare system, the film follows Lazarescu through institutions unable to offer the attention he needs.²⁶² Ironic codes of continuity are revealed in Lazarescu’s apartment where he sits amongst prominent gas pipes, a reminder of disruptions to central heating during the 1980s. In the hallway the characters are indifferent to the lights turning off, perhaps used to the socialist illumination systems when light and darkness ran

²⁵⁹ Alice Baran, “Aftereffects of 1989,” 16.

²⁶⁰ Robert A. Rosenstone, “History in Images/History in Words: Reflections on the Possibility of Really Putting History onto Film,” *American Historical Review* 93 (December 1988): 1173–85.

²⁶¹ Andrew O. Scott, review: In “12:08 East of Bucharest a Romanian Town Slouches Toward Revolution and Beyond,” *New York Times*, June 13, 2007, <https://www.nytimes.com/2007/06/06/movies/06scot.html>.

²⁶² *The Death of Mr. Lazarescu*, directed by Cristi Puiu Prods, Alexandru Munteanu, Bobby Păunescu and Anca Puiu (Mandragora, 2005), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/the-death-of-mr-lazarescu>.

on schedule according to infrequent supply.²⁶³ Not much has changed, then. Certainly, the effectiveness of healthcare has not. In 2019, one in four Romanians had insufficient access to healthcare, according to *The Economist*.²⁶⁴ Indeed, the European liberation from Communism to capitalism has not resolved the health crisis, membership enabling a mass exodus of professionals: since joining the EU, 20,000 doctors have left to work abroad. A dire conclusion in real life is reflected in *Lazarescu*: “Better not get ill in Romania.”²⁶⁵

But *Lazarescu* is a funny film. In a society undergoing transitions, this is the humour of lost confidence and disorientation. The apartment scene is replete with black humour, his neighbours are more interested in how to cook quince jelly than helping Lazarescu. Mostly, the camera ignores him. Even when he vomits blood, the neighbour’s offer of pork moussaka is comic rather than concerning, thus disabling him any real sympathy. Perhaps avoiding intimacy with Lazarescu’s illness confirms Charlie Chaplin’s diagnosis of the aesthetics of tragicomedy: “Life is a tragedy when seen in close-up, but a comedy in long-shot.”²⁶⁶ However, this film also provides a close-up of the tragedy of the Romanian present. *Lazarescu* was intended as a morality tale, a representation of “Love Thy Neighbour,” exploring the tension of living virtuously in a liminal and lonely society. Mioara, the ambulance driver, serves as the Good Samaritan. She accompanies Lazarescu as he is turned away by crowded, or complacent, hospitals, but becomes attached to his frailty. As does the viewer. For Paul Arthur, the crowded frames and claustrophobic camerawork stimulate a “sense of urgency about what *isn’t* being done.” The viewer is trapped in traffic too, in a state of “general intellectual angst,” as the system fails Lazarescu. Waiting with Mioara, as in image 3, “Time doesn’t simply hang, it crushes.”²⁶⁷

²⁶³ Alina Haliliuc, “What Is So Funny about *The Death of Mr Lazarescu*?” *The Journal of Popular Culture* 48 (2015): 161.

²⁶⁴ “Romania’s health-care system, the EU’s worst, struggles to reform,” *The Economist*, November 21, 2019, <https://www.economist.com/europe/2019/11/21/romania-health-care-system-the-eus-worst-struggles-to-reform>.

²⁶⁵ “Romania’s health-care system,” *The Economist*.

²⁶⁶ Harry M. Geduld, ed., *Charlie Chaplin’s Own Story* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2019), 156.

²⁶⁷ Paul Arthur, “Habeas Corpus: A Mediation on *The Death of Mr Lazarescu* and Corporeal Cinema,” *Film Comment* 42 (2006): 44–49. Image taken from “The Death of Mr. Lazarescu (Cristi Puiu, 2005),” *Senses of Cinema*, <https://www.sensesofcinema.com/2017/cteq/the-death-of-mr-lazarescu/>.

Image 3: Mioara becomes the sole charge for Lazarescu's treatment, in Puiu's 2005 film, *The Death of Mr Lazarescu*.

In neorealist style, this film captures human kindness alongside institutional crisis, choreographed to implicate the viewer. In some ways, the film could be read as concerned with blame. Lazarescu's suffering increases as people attribute his condition to drinking. Perhaps this blame, and absence of sympathy, is code for Western treatment of Romania, past and present, in its conditionality for creating a European Family. Indeed, as Georgescu theorises, "ironic messages are characterised by a certain richness that allows them to perform memory work and socio-political critiques simultaneously."²⁶⁸ *Lazarescu* is about fellowship, which the West *should* pay to its Eastern neighbour. The film does not depict a glorious capitalist modernity and the closing shot of Lazarescu's corpse confronts the film's namesake. "Lazarus" is not revived but left to die by a system distracted by other crises, and the viewer is left confronting what it means to be an individual in the post-socialist world.

However, nostalgic redress for a disappointing present is challenged in Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days* (2007), which explores the claustrophobic reality of living in a pro-natalist and hyper-surveillant state. Ceaușescu enforced an aggressive policy that criminalised abortion. His aim was to reach a population of 25 million and the biopolitics of his regime represented

²⁶⁸ Diana Georgescu, "Ceaușescu Hasn't Died: Irony as Counter-memory in Post-Socialist Romania," as quoted in Maria Todorova and Zsuzsa Gille, eds., *Post-Communist Nostalgia* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2012), 171.

motherhood as a patriotic duty.²⁶⁹ Indeed, members of the Western Bloc praised Romania for its resurgence in population when the World Population Conference was held in Bucharest in 1974. Unsurprisingly, legislation forced abortions dangerously underground, and abortions became the leading cause of mortality among fertile women between 1966 and 1989.²⁷⁰ Mungiu remembers this tragedy.

The film arrives immediately in the drama, with no backstory about Gabita's pregnancy or friendship with Otilia.²⁷¹ This immediacy is intensified by frequent silence. This is destabilising and asks us, according to Mungiu, "to wrestle with our thoughts, as they wrestle with theirs."²⁷² After the abortion, and after the rape of both women by the doctor, the camera focuses for fourteen seconds on Otilia's bowed head, and it is another fourteen minutes before she speaks again. Silence demands we watch without distraction, experiencing the brutality and extent of female subjugation.²⁷³ Rather than witness the "action," we witness the emotional impact of Otilia and Gabita's realities. During the rape of the women, the viewer experiences close-ups of the other woman's facial expressions. So too for the abortion itself, which is seen through Otilia's anxiety as she is trapped at a dinner party with her boyfriend's family. The camera alternates between front- and back-shots, suggesting a vulnerability as observed by the guests as much as the state. Women were day-to-day victims of the policies of the same Communist Romania that the "West" praised in 1974.

This vulnerability is also discernible in the spaces the women are pictured in. The film scholar Anna Batori suggests that the camera materialises the fear of the regime via a grey palette, narrow streets, and dilapidated buildings.²⁷⁴ But the camerawork also materialises the specific *female* experience. In the opening scene, symbolic windows of escape, including a window and a suitcase, jar with the entrapping fishbowl. Gabita is only captured in interior spaces, invaded by frontal camera shots and over-the-shoulder frames, suggesting an intrusive and omnipresent surveillance. The scenes with Dr Bebe convey this oppressive inescapability. Not only does his frame dominate the twenty-minute shot preceding the abortion, leaving the women peripheral in frame and freedom, but Laura Ceia argues that the viewer is invited to feel disgusted by his explicit biological

²⁶⁹ Anna Batori, "Power and acts of resistance in Cristian Mungiu's *4 months, 3 weeks, 2 days*," *Studies in Eastern European Cinema* 7 (2016): 130.

²⁷⁰ Valerie Palmer-Mehta and Alina Haliliuc, "The Performance of Silence in Cristian Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks, and 2 Days*," *Text and Performance Quarterly* 31 (2011): 114.

²⁷¹ *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days*, directed by Cristian Mungiu, produced by Oleg Mutu (Mobra Films, 2007), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/4-months-3-weeks-and-2-days>.

²⁷² Palmer-Mehta and Haliliuc, "The Performance of Silence," 111, 121.

²⁷³ Deb Margolin as quoted in Palmer-Mehta and Haliliuc, "The Performance of Silence," 177.

²⁷⁴ Batori, "Power and acts," 136.

language.²⁷⁵ Disgust is prompted by the hyper-real sounds of latex and, as an affective emotion, insists on a reckoning with the normative realities of the time.

Image 4: Otilia invites the audience to confront alternative memories of Communism, in Mungiu's 2007 film, *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days*.

432 exemplifies Roumania Deltcheva's "cinematic remembrance," calling for a confrontation with the Romanian past.²⁷⁶ If films can be persuasively affective, as Laura Ceia suggests, this one *persuades* of untold dramas outside the purview of the narrative.²⁷⁷ These women symbolise all women "raped" by the Communist state. An invitation for moral contemplation is explicit in the final scene when Otilia looks directly at the camera (Figure 4), introducing the possibility of the viewer's own complicity: a sense of guilt in watching what "usually goes neither acknowledged nor understood."²⁷⁸

RNW remembered Communism as everything from pro-natalist brutality to bureaucratic absurdity. In capturing such diversity, RNW legitimised alternative relationships with

²⁷⁵ Laura Ceia, "Flee, Avoid, Ignore, Suppress: Physical and Socio-moral Disgust as quoted in Cristian Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days*," *Journal of Research in Gender Studies* 1 (2011): 176.

²⁷⁶ Roumania Deltcheva, "Reliving the Past in East European Cinema" in *Eastern European Cinemas*, edited by Aniko Imre (Milton Park: Taylor and Francis, 2005), 204–210.

²⁷⁷ Ceia, "Flee, Avoid, Ignore, Suppress," 166.

²⁷⁸ Roxana Cazan, "Constructing Spaces of Dissent in Communist Romania: Ruined Bodies and Clandestine Spaces in Cristian Mungiu's '4 Months, 3 Weeks, and 2 Days'" and Gabriela Adamesteanu's "A Few Days in the Hospital," *Women's Studies Quarterly* 39 (2011): 94; Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 202. Image taken from Chen, Xi. "How '4 Months, 3 Weeks, and 2 Days' Tells a Story," *Physician Writer*, June 29, 2021, <https://medium.com/physician-writer/how-4-months-3-weeks-and-2-days-tells-a-story-27e8e7556469>.

Communism, contemporary realities, and concomitant commemoration. Mungiu, like his compatriots, called for a restoration of the individual, inscribing in his films “the idea that something very small that happens to you is as good a subject as a saga.”²⁷⁹ The next section qualifies the extent to which his call was answered.

The Reception of RNW

RNW films were important cultural capital, serving to project an identity on an international stage. They fared inconsistently, but generally received less domestic acclaim, scholarly hypotheses for this apathy ranged from ordinary Romanians uninterested in seeing their realities on screen, unable to access one of only 68 cinemas in 2010 (the same year the *Los Angeles Times* gushed that Romania could not make a bad film), or suspicious that RNW undermined the politics of clamouring for international recognition.²⁸⁰ A *Palme d’Or* is hardly redemptive for the 22% of the population living below the poverty line.²⁸¹ This section suggests that diverse responses point to the way that memory functions: filmmakers did not make authoritative memories, but the spectators co-authored what was commemorated, taking from these films what they wanted to find meanings that served their present.

The negotiation of commemorating Communism in RNW depended on the spatial and temporal distance of the viewer. Media and memory scholars suggest that “what is personal in our own memories is confirmed by the memories of others,” and what constitutes the collective memory of the past is negotiated in its collective consumption.²⁸² Films form part of this discourse, viewership part of the textual community demanded of collectives. The inescapability of the West extended to the dissemination of films, film festivals being important spaces to legitimise the artistic value of Romanian cinema.²⁸³ Extensive reliance on technological expertise and funding also hinted at the power of Europe in tangible relationships.²⁸⁴ The extent to which the West commands the global imaginary of Romania was further complicated by this pragmatic reliance regarding the cinema industry. As much as RNW queried the relationship Romania has with its past and with Europe, *Eurimages* endowments came with European expectations.

²⁷⁹ Karin Badt, “Interview with Cristian Mungiu,” *Film Criticism* 34 (2010): 105.

²⁸⁰ Elena Roxan Popan, “Recent Romanian Cinema: Is it a Real New Wave or Just a Splash in the Water?” *The Communication Review* 17 (2014): 229–232; David Lindvall, “Film International 55: The Romanian New Wave,” *Film* (2012) <http://filmint.nu/?p=4264>; Bogdan Popa in Constantin Parvulescu and Turcus Turcus, “Devices of Cultural Europeanisation,” *Studies in Eastern European Cinema* 9 (2018): 9–11.

²⁸¹ Marissa Field, “Top 10 Facts about Living Conditions in Romania,” *Borgen Project*, accessed on July 14, 2019, <https://borgenproject.org/top-10-facts-about-living-conditions-in-romania/>.

²⁸² John Storey and Andrew Hoskins, as quoted in Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 26, 144.

²⁸³ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema,” 30–34.

²⁸⁴ Diana Iordanova, “East Europe’s Cinema Industries Since 1989: Financing Structures and Studios,” *Journal of the European Institute for Communication and Culture* 6 (1999): 47–54.

The reception and consumption of film intersects with memory, in that people watch films not so much to expand perceptions, but to have them confirmed. Hugo Mercier's exploration of "myside bias," that we seek evidence that accords with existing beliefs, is relevant in the way that audiences have approached RNW.²⁸⁵ However, the aesthetics through which commemoration was articulated in RNW, as well as the subjects of commemoration, confronted the "myside bias" of the West, and problematised the "dominant opinions" of the Romanian past.²⁸⁶ That said, international audiences have also been willing to watch films that trouble their preconceptions. RNW, by articulating memories that insisted on a constitutive gap between reality and its cinematic representation, offered possibilities to audiences navigating historical memorialisation in postmodern, transnational spaces. In some ways, the success of RNW was the cause and consequence of broader revisions to commemorative discourse. The awards heaped on RNW suggest the films epitomised a moment in which the right to narrate the past was no longer reserved for academic and political elites.²⁸⁷ Revisions to historical truths have been taking place in various spaces, suggesting a common calling for the democratisation of history and a receptive public.²⁸⁸ The calls RNW made were the early stages of a global chorus. *Lazarescu* alone received an *Un certain regard* at Cannes (2005), *The Silver Orb Award* (Alba Regia 2005), *The Golden Tower* (Palic 2005), *The Grand Prix of the Jury* at the International Copenhagen Film Festival (2005), and many more. Audiences, at least those acclimatised to arthouse aesthetics, found in RNW a grammar that "felt" true.

However, some reviews hint at the prevalence of the condemning imaginary of Romanian history, Romania as incapable of cultural creativity, and Romania as filtered through politicised discourse. Patronising pejoratives that films were "slow-paced and unexciting" (12:08), suggest audiences wanted more from history being made "by the humble and foolish."²⁸⁹ Others found respite via "exotic rides into ... forbidden territory," appreciable only from the position of a non-implicated subject.²⁹⁰ The lives in *Tales* were golden, with their "sour beauty" and glimpse into the "Romanian spirit" of camaraderie, but only because their "absurdity and distance from today grant

²⁸⁵ Hugo Mercier and Dan Sperber, *The Enigma of Reason* (London: Allen Lane, 2017).

²⁸⁶ Chun Cheng, et al., "Social bots and mass media manipulated public opinion through dual opinion climate," *Chinese Physics B* 31 (2021): 3.

²⁸⁷ Zandberg, "Ketchup in the Auschwitz of Tomatoes," 111.

²⁸⁸ Johanna Zetterstrom-Sharp and Chris Wingfield, "A "Safe Space" to Debate Colonial Legacy? The University of Cambridge Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology and the Campaign to Return a Looted Benin Altarpiece to Nigeria," *Museum Worlds: Advances in Research* 7 (2019): 1–9.

²⁸⁹ Anthony Kao, "Review: 12:08, East of Bucharest," *Cinema Escapist*, January 30, 2015, <https://www.cinemaescapist.com/2015/01/review-1208-east-of-bucharest-romania-2006/>; Don Groves, "If I Want to Whistle, I Whistle Review," *SBS*, June 10, 2010, <https://www.sbs.com.au/movies/review/if-i-want-whistle-i-whistle-review>.

²⁹⁰ Filimon, "Reviewed Work(s)," 55.

it a nostalgic aura.”²⁹¹ Reviews seem to reveal a pervasive perspective that Romanian films were too homemade for audiences acclimatised to particular cinematic norms. Interestingly, the trailer of *432* in America metamorphosed the film into an action movie, selling a fast-paced narrative revolving around a secret, quasi-murder mystery, *à la* James Cameron. Faintings at screenings hint at an unpreparedness for a film more concerned with an exploration of the repressed realities of private life that Mungiu called to “Remember” when it was broadcast in Romania.²⁹² Realities were packaged according to a global aesthetic and a global narrative, and then contextualised. The Romanian revolution, supposedly a “historical novelty,”²⁹³ was, for Peter Bradshaw, confirmed as significant in *432*: “On Marinca’s face there is spiritual devastation ... It was from wretchedness and rage such as this that bred the uprising that changed Romania and the world.”²⁹⁴ He seems to miss the coded commentary of the consequences of female suppression.

These selective “accommodations” of RNW confirm the theory of Hegemonic Ideology outlined by film scholar Todd Gitlin, which he understands as the reproduction of a dominant narrative via cultural mediums.²⁹⁵ RNW, concerned with a past outside the global imaginary, had to balance between guessing at audience desires and tolerances if they wanted to “speak to them.”²⁹⁶ But tolerances are hard to shift, especially because the value-laden attributes Cristian Tileaga finds applied by post-Communist memory politics were *constituted* by the finality of the Tismăneanu Report.²⁹⁷ Communism had been first, silenced, and second, categorically demonised, and so audiences lacked the *capacity* to absorb messages that destabilised dominant systems of meaning. Therefore, whilst the hegemonic system is not “cut-and-dried,” it processes non-hegemonic ideology into the hegemonic system precisely so it remains hegemonic. The West digested RNW to fit their preconceptions, celebrating some aspects, or excluding material that was too “oppositional” in form, returning it “to the cultural margins from which it came.”²⁹⁸

Such moulding is explored by the cultural historians Oana Godeanu-Kenworthy and Oana Popescu-Sandu in relation to the American reception of *432*. The film was broadcast when reproductive rights were potent in political debates. They suggest that the American public

²⁹¹ Filimon, “Reviewed Work(s),” 55.

²⁹² Dominique Nasta, *Contemporary Romanian Cinema: The History of an Unexpected Miracle* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2013), 197.

²⁹³ Timothy Garton Ash in Stefano Bottoni and Sean Lambert, *Long Awaited West: Eastern Europe Since 1944* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2017), 177.

²⁹⁴ As quoted in Nasta, *Contemporary Romanian Cinema*, 197.

²⁹⁵ Todd Gitlin, “Prime Time Ideology: The Hegemonic Process in Television Entertainment,” *Social Problems* 26 (1979): 251–252.

²⁹⁶ Gitlin, “Prime Time Ideology,” 263.

²⁹⁷ Cristian Tileaga, “Communism in Retrospect: The Rhetoric of Historical Representation and Writing the Collective Memory of Recent Past,” *Memory Studies* 5 (2012): 466.

²⁹⁸ Gitlin, “Prime Time Ideology,” 264.

transformed the film into “the controversial nature of particular individual choices within the liberal capitalist paradigm,” politicised in an atmosphere of pro-life-pro-choice controversy.²⁹⁹ That the film was used on both sides of the abortion debate is interesting, because it illustrates the individuality of filmic deconstruction. It could be a “pro-choice film” by displaying the traumatic options left when women are denied options, but it could equally be enlisted by the National Right to Life website as an invitation to consider that “an abortion not only costs a helpless victim his or her life but also extracts a considerable chunk of humanity of those who take that life.”³⁰⁰ Godeanu-Kenworthy and Popescu-Sandu conclude that global entertainment has not eroded place- and space-specific spectatorship: *432* shows that stories “are filtered twice: first through their own cultural lens, and then through that of the destination country.”³⁰¹

At the domestic level, *432* was consumed differently. Contemporary commentator Christina Anghelina found a warning against nostalgia in the unflinching exposure of tragedy, and for present-day audiences, it is an instruction “that the solution for the problems of the present is not and can never be found in the past, but in the future.” The writer Iulia Blaga thought it exposed the unresolved legacy of moral corruption. Maria Andries, writing in the mainstream press, finds comment on the lack of restorative accountability: “The victims, socialized in an ancient culture of guilt, won’t talk. And the culprits count on it, as they always do.”³⁰² Pro-choice is not the lens through which the film was filtered in Romania, but the relationship the present has with the past. Romanian audiences were sometimes contemptuous of the RNW movement. On the one hand, this was because the grim aesthetics that troubled a positive self-image were “doomed to lose” against Hollywood fare.³⁰³ On the other hand, it was because Communism had left the film industry gutted, and therefore guaranteed a legacy of uncompetitive production companies.³⁰⁴ Indeed, to finance *12:08* Porumboiu had to persuade a milk factory and a bakery to cover his costs.³⁰⁵ For others, especially generations whose memories of Communism were formed in the 1950s and therefore before state censorship had exorcised the Gulags from public consciousness, nostalgic renderings like those offered in *Tales* were not only inappropriate but fetishized falsities. Mungiu himself said that “for us it was half funny that the lights would be cut off for two hours

²⁹⁹ Godeanu-Kenworthy and Popescu-Sandu, “From Minimalist Representation,” 225.

³⁰⁰ D. Andrusko, “The most persuasive anti-abortion argument, ever?” *National Right To Life News* (2008), www.nrlc.org/archive/news/2008/NRL03/Argument.html.

³⁰¹ Godeanu-Kenworthy and Popescu-Sandu, “From Minimalist Representation,” 244.

³⁰² All in Godeanu-Kenworthy, “From Minimalist Representation,” 235.

³⁰³ Imre, *East European Cinemas*, 1.

³⁰⁴ Iona Uricaru, “Follow the Money: Financing Contemporary Cinema in Romania,” as quoted in Aniko Imre, ed, *A Companion to Eastern European Cinema* (New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons, 2012), 6.

³⁰⁵ Andy Ridley, “California Dreamin,” *Socialist Review*, June 1, 2008, <http://socialistreview.org.uk/326/california-dreamin>.

in the night ... and we wouldn't have to do our homework."³⁰⁶ This attitude, and its presentation in film, was insensitive for Smaranda Vultur: "To me, they seem to belittle the evil of that time, to dismiss as derisive the things that literally ruined my life."³⁰⁷ Disenchantment with RNW and what it called to commemorate is confirmed by viewing figures: domestic films had just 2.5% share of the market in 2010.³⁰⁸ RNW revised a past and critiqued a present that some of its people preferred to ignore.

The context in which RNW was being made and consumed also explains their initial domestic rejection. For the film-scholar Doru Pop, these films struggled because they were perceived as denigrating Romania on the international stage, a stage upon which post-communist Romanians searched for their national brand.³⁰⁹ This self-presentation concerned both national patriotism and international promotion, amplified in the \$20-million touristic campaign in 2004, "*The always surprising Romania*." But this did not trickle into self-confidence: an IRES study in May 2013 showed almost 60% of Romanians believed Romania was negatively perceived in Europe.³¹⁰ Pop suggests that due to the international receptivity and consequent visibility of RNW, films were part of the problem. RNW satirised Romanian history in self-effacing discourse and ridiculed present-day Romania as lacking rules and morals. RNW, by pedalling a "runner-up" attitude, confirmed the imaginary that Romania was a space of parody.³¹¹ Given that parody works when it contains an element of truth, ironized nostalgia for Communism may have been uncomfortable domestically *because* it was appropriate in relation to the present. For Romanians interested in positive projections, these films were an unwelcome confirmation of "how the continent has struggled to shake off the legacy of dictatorship."³¹² At the same time, the approval of Western audiences for RNW played into the need for recognition. Better to be seen as intrepid idiots that not be seen at all. Paradoxically, RNW was both a source of tension and tribulation when understood as contributory to the European framework.

³⁰⁶ Nick Bradshaw, "Where There's Pomp ... Cristian Mungiu on Tales from the Golden Age," *BFI*, April 19, 2014, <https://www2.bfi.org.uk/news/where-there-s-pomp-cristian-mungiu- Tales-golden-age>.

³⁰⁷ Smaranda Vultur, "Daily Life and Constraints in Communist Romania in the Late 1980s: From the Semiotics of Food to the Semiotics of Power" as quoted in Maria Todorova, Augusta Dimou, and Stefan Troebst, eds., *Remembering Communism: Private and Public Recollections of Lived Experience in Southeast Europe* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2014), 175.

³⁰⁸ "Cinema of Romania", *Wikipedia*, accessed September 5, 2022, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cinema_of_Romania#Romanian_cinema_\(1990%E2%80%93present\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cinema_of_Romania#Romanian_cinema_(1990%E2%80%93present)).

³⁰⁹ Doru Pop, "An Analysis of Romanians' Self-Image in Contemporary Cinematographic," *Metacritic Journal for Comparative Studies and Theory* 1 (2015): 139.

³¹⁰ Pop, "An Analysis of Romanians' Self-Image," 143.

³¹¹ Daskalov and Mishkova, *Entangled Histories*, 36.

³¹² R. Jefferson and A. Timu, "Most Shocking Revolution of 1989 Still Casts a Shadow on Europe," *Bloomberg*, November 6, 2019, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/features/2019-11-06/romania-news-30-years-after-fall-of-communism-remains-unsettled>.

Romanians did begin to enjoy RNW, at least the cosmopolitan members from whose ranks such films were coming. Cultural historian Onoriu Colacel suggests that Romanian films foster an internal culture of belonging.³¹³ The linguist Rodica Ieta argues that RNW enabled audiences to practice critical intellectual engagement, celebrated as a rejection of socialist realism having suffered it for so long.³¹⁴ The neorealist metaphors were, for Shohat, affective for communities that felt unrepresented in a transnational context, analogical identifications offering a “compensatory outlet.”³¹⁵ Nonetheless, positive feelings for RNW were rare. Films that showed “truth 24 frames/second,” often exposing the truth of the present, could hardly be popular whilst the present *was* dissatisfying.³¹⁶ The aesthetics of minimalism, with its “gloomy mix” of angst and sadness touched too close a nerve,³¹⁷ and dark and desperate films alienated a public “ashamed of being a Romanian.”³¹⁸ Puiu recognised this tension: “This is the commercial recipe...you go to the movies, watch Steven Seagal saving the world and return home serene. What about when he does not save it; now you've got a problem! Commercial cinema cannot solve your own drama.”³¹⁹ Hollywood heroes might not solve twenty-first century Romanian realities. But RNW reminded and remembered too many dramas for a public desperate to move on.

³¹³ Onoriu Colacel, *The Romanian Cinema of Nationalism: Historical Films as Propaganda and Spectacle* (Jefferson: McFarland and Company, 2018), 167.

³¹⁴ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema,” 29.

³¹⁵ Shohat and Stam, *Unthinking Eurocentrism*, 351.

³¹⁶ Alexandru Leo Serban, Ramona Uritescu-Lombard, Rodica Ieta and Maria Ionita, “Romanian Cinema: From Modernity to Neo-Realism,” *Film Criticism* 34 (2010): 17.

³¹⁷ Serban et al., “Romanian Cinema,” 4.

³¹⁸ Dan Berindei as cited in Imre, *A Companion*, 7.

³¹⁹ Puiu as quoted in Lindvall, “Film International 55.”

Conclusion

What next for RNW? What next for the memory of Romanian history, in and outside Romania, in and from films? Has RNW invoked a reassessment of what counts as the Romanian past and democratised the construction of what constitutes cultural memories? RNW is over. Whilst films are still being made and legitimated, the commitment to reframing a troubled past, as well as the specific context of negotiating a European space, have faded. Audiences everywhere are increasingly willing to treat history critically. RNW was contextual, made when this willingness was embryonic, evidenced by the criticism some of the films received. The appropriateness of irony was a response to a particular millennial moment, a society responding to a contextual set of pressures about Romania in Europe and dealing with the fallout of a failed revolution, at least one that had failed to bring about the transformation expected of it.

However, Romania is still being framed as a backwater by stakeholders in the European Project, be they journalists, populist politicians, or public figures. These perspectives continue to be felt *in* Romania. The framing of such perspectives continues to be within a dialogue of blaming a Communist past for a failed capitalist present.³²⁰ In 2012, the film-scholar Antonia Kovacheva remarked, “there is still an expectation of sad movies originating in the shantytown ghetto South-East from Vienna.”³²¹ As long as these frameworks persevere, there remains a space for films that critically commemorate what it means to be Romanian. RNW might have finished, but its legacy need not. We should keep thinking about Romanian memory, and its articulation, in a “new wave” way. This means neither amnesia nor anamnesis but accommodating both official and vernacular dimensions of Communist memory. The writer Mohai Rusu calls this type of commemoration “comprehensive memory,” and, in Romania, this means the de-exceptionalisation of Romanian Communism as the history of trauma and tragedy. If 41% of Romanians did not feel that the regime was a criminal one in 2010, then it was not the “devil in history” right-wing intellectuals had insisted.³²² Rusu says that the German Sabrow-Kommission should be the model for “working through” Communism, but Romania hardly needs to look West for its prototype.³²³ RNW offers a domestic blueprint for a critical historicization of Communism. “New wave” commemoration means bottom-up history and individual memories, it means nuance in the construction of cultural

³²⁰ “Huge protests force Romania’s government to reverse itself on corruption,” *The Economist*, February 11, 2017, <https://www.economist.com/europe/2017/02/11/huge-protests-force-romanias-government-to-reverse-itself-on-corruption>.

³²¹ As quoted in Lindvall, “Film International 55.”

³²² Report in Mihai Stelian Rusu, “Transitional Politics of Memory: Political Strategies of Managing the Past in Post-communist Romania,” *Europe-Asia Studies* 69 (2017): 1272.

³²³ Rusu, “Transitional Politics of Memory,” 1270–1276.

collectives, and it means confronting the framework that decides who and what counts as the past, and who and what counts as its lyricists.

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